

OpEd - Light “photons” **Cannot** **Possibly** be a Real Particle

I’m only calling this an OpEd, because this is not a detailed Quantum discussion. From a macro-logical and thermodynamics perspective: what is light since it is **not** a particle (nor a wave)?

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(With R. Ashcroft’s Commentary)

Best Viewed At: <https://bit.ly/3pnBLOX>

ABSTRACT

In Plasma-electromagnetism (PEM) Theory, we postulate the existence of an EM-centered dynamic force, and this includes *some form* of aetherism. The exact anatomy has not been decided. However, we rely upon circuit theories, and not upon physical matter for mass, as Charge (Q) becomes the core of the PEMF and all Unified Field Theories concerning forces, motion, gravitics, energy, dynamics and statics, including thermodynamics and QED/QCD. The use of Magnetohydrodynamics is relegated to a secondary/confirmatory use, while plasma High Energy Physics is primary in the study. Furthermore, in PEMF we do not need a ball light photonic theory, as will be touched upon in some detail in this Opinion Editorial. This fact is somewhat bolstered by the fact that electrons can be “created” by photonic pairing in low energy situations, meaning that the polar circuit model is a better postulate.¹

Key Words: light - photon - electron - Kirchoff - Planck - circuit - thermodynamics

¹ <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/news/149087/scientists-discover-turn-light-into-matter/>

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Short Historiography: Wave-Particle Duality Theory

The atomic theory has come a long way. It was obstructed by unipolar (incomplete) rationalism², a materialist-reductionist position prompted first by Aristotle³ and later by men such as Descartes, and this kept better truths from being revealed. But within a short period of time (and after spectroscopy was discovered in the 1840s, owing to its rich history going back to John Dee and Sir Isaac Newton's optics work⁴), it evolved like so:

- | | |
|--|---------|
| 1. Atoms - indivisible balls | 400 BCE |
| 2. Weber's Electrodynamical model ⁵ | 1860 |
| 3. Plum Pudding model - a mix of positive and negative charges | 1904 |
| 4. Nuclear model | 1911 |
| 5. Electron Orbital model | 1913 |
| 6. Orbital-Valence model | 1916 |
| 7. Wave-Particle Duality model of Light ⁶ | 1923 |
| 8. Quantum/Light Nuclear model ⁷ | 1925 |
| 9. Weak and Strong Force Nuclear model | 1960s |
| 10. And now... Structured Atomic Model ^{8 9 10 11 12} | 2015? |

However, the 10th does not arise from the 9th, but from the 4th and modifies the next few models, along with a modification of the origins of Gravity. This owes not only to the work of Velikovsky¹³ and Hannes Alfvén¹⁴, but to the reservations of Newton and Einstein themselves. Newton, very likely, had access to Gilbert's work¹⁵, and was challenged on his model's lack of connection mechanism. He felt, almost assuredly, that Gravity would be relegated to a secondary effect of The Force¹⁶, which back then was not understood¹⁷. But cults surrounding the mystic genius¹⁸ stayed strong through the era of the Royal Society for hundreds of years.

² https://www.academia.edu/68876325/Response_to_Crothers_Exposition_of_Unimodular_Defect

³ <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Aristotle/Physics-and-metaphysics>

⁴ <http://strangebeautiful.com/other-texts/newton-opticks-4ed.pdf>

⁵ <http://www.ifi.unicamp.br/~assis/Weber-in-English-Vol-1.pdf>

⁶ with Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle, 1927

⁷ the addition of Boltzman's observations to chemistry

⁸ <http://ikkem.com/iccf23/orppt/ICCF23-OA-04%20Kaal.pdf>

⁹ <https://structuredatom.org/>

¹⁰ <https://etherealmatters.org/sam>

¹¹ <https://structuredatom.org/atomizer/atom-viewer>

¹² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/atomic-models/sam>

¹³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/velikovsky>

¹⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pu-research/h-alfven>

¹⁵ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1A9oPx8jSE3hAYiykSbGY7L13KiSncli/view>

¹⁶ UAF = PEM Force:

https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EP EMC

¹⁷ Newton: 17th century, EM theory: 19th Century

¹⁸ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

Furthermore, after spectroscopy “proved” the sun was a ball of “burning” hydrogen¹⁹, it didn’t take long for the Royal Society and the likes of Lord Kelvin - enemy of Oliver Heaviside²⁰ - to decide that gravity produced light. How? Why: atom smashing, of course. Later, quantum physicists “made it so”²¹ even while in secretive, unknown plasma labs of greats like Langmuir or Bostick were busy proving fusion could happen in small fusors²² and in relatively low energy conditions. Therefore, it was a byproduct of the Electric Sun²³, and not the cause of the solar radiation, let alone the “solar wind” and electric²⁴ and magnetic fields of the sun.

So, what is the matter with the Standard Model as it is? Setting aside its failure to deal with the *obvious* interrelations of the Force... changing orders of magnitude inside the atom because of distances... the main issue is that the nucleus is *undefined*. Why would neutrons help glue protons together? Why would you need more neutrons than protons in most isotopes? Why do quanta modify the nucleus, and why the orbitals? Why do the orbitals take these specific shapes? Why can light do the magical things relativity says it can?

These queries are not dealt with in the Standard Model, but they are easily dealt with in an Electrodynamical model. So we backtrack the model to Weber first²⁵, then forward through the charge experiments, circuit theory, Maxwell et al., and then to the Structured Atomic Model with an enhanced understanding of light’s real nature (SAM2). We will lay out a philosophical or metaphysical basis for light, and a more physical discussion. Also, we will (briefly) talk about the strange case of Kirchoff, a man who could have helped us all avoid this issue, except for one glaring problem, now revealed by Dr. Robitaille in a series of experiments.²⁶

10 Reasons Photons are Not Real Particles²⁷

Listing them out, first, will be the most efficient means of conveyance:

1. Photons are a model only of discrete quantized energy exchange²⁸, occurring at scales of the Planck length²⁹, owing to the fact that $e = h\nu$, where ν is the frequency of the oscillating quanta, and h is Planck’s wave constant³⁰.

¹⁹

<https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/how-scientists-discovered-helium-first-alien-element-1868-1809-70057/>

²⁰ <https://euro-math-soc.eu/review/forgotten-genius-oliver-heaviside-maverick-electrical-science>

²¹ Ie - leaned upon cults of personality, fame, and name dropping like Einstein.

²² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pe-research/fusors>

²³ Juerges/Alfven/Scott

²⁴ <https://now.uiowa.edu/2021/07/physicists-led-university-iowa-more-fully-describe-suns-electric-field>

²⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/weber>

²⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/robitaille>

²⁷ Ie - not atomic like balls of matter.

²⁸ Discovered by Boltzmann https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_quantum_mechanics

²⁹ <https://www.britannica.com/science/Planck-length>

³⁰ $6.62607004 \times 10^{-34} \text{ m}^2 \text{ kg} / \text{ s}$

2. Light alters its “speed” instantly³¹ upon changing mediums, and therefore would violate thermodynamics and physical restrictions of matter, and ergo **can not, ever, under any conditions** be a real particle.
3. Therefore light has no mass, and *cannot* impart momentum.³²
4. All “momentum” imparted is charge related (exchange of energy states) owing to the circuit nature of light, and the Biefeld-Brown Effect³³ in an electromagnetic environment.³⁴
5. Light does not bend due to gravity, it reacts to the PEMF directly, and we see this because all “macro lensing” occurs at R=1, and not elsewhere in space³⁵... or else all light everywhere would be bent and the sky quite a mess to look at.
6. Light cannot be a particle or it would achieve a maximal spread before forming mottled concentration and dilution regions away from the source.
7. Reflections are continuations of the circuit, and the surfaces’ interactions form the “load” on the circuit, hence the reduction in luminosity, frequency (shift), and dissipation.
8. The geometric reflection might be convenient to model as a tennis ball (kinetic bounce), however, it is owed to the polar rotation due to the true nature of *i*, the “imaginary number”, which is actually the following identity matrix:

$$i = \sqrt{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

³¹ “On what basis can the claim be made that photons change speed instantly, particularly when we cannot measure the change or the period over which it occurs. We do not have devices that can sample (clock) at a time period of 575 Peta Hertz or faster. To achieve these clocks we are using ElectroMagnetic Radiation of frequencies higher than Hard UV, and this sort of light damages the structure of atoms. Given we cannot detect a time transition to photon velocity does not prove that the change in velocity is instant. We simply do not have the required detectors to show that it is an instant change. ElectroMagnetic Radiation does heat the medium through which it travels, and this is known. Further the number of photons entering the medium is not the same as the number of photons leaving the medium. Photons are reflected, diffracted, refracted, absorbed and frequencies are transformed to usually by frequency decrease but there are cases of frequency increase. All these factors shows that Thermodynamics is not violated and this the claim made has no basis, and the conclusion cannot be sustained.” ~R. Ashcroft, “Nature of Things”

³² “This claim is not supported by actual experiments, consider the following article.
<https://www.princeton.edu/~romalis/PHYS312/Coulomb%20Ref/Photonmasslimits.pdf>

This is just one of many that show that photons have mass, regardless the equations for determining Energy of the Photon requires that Photons have mass other wise the equations related do not work. Neutrinos must have mass for exactly the same reasons. I have hearsay claim that supports my speculation that Neutrinos are an extreme frequency Photon, and maybe some day the fact will be actually published. Regardless of this you cannot claim that neutrinos and photons have momentum when the claim that they are massless is dictated. Momentum requires mass in order for it to exist.” ~Ashcroft.

My reply to this is that these experiments came out AFTER the presumption of momentum, and not from direct measurement of any.

³³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/tt-brown>

³⁴ In the case of Voyager, the solar electric field.

³⁵

<https://www.amazon.com/Discourses-Mathematical-Illustrations-Electrodynamics-Transformations/dp/0963447157/>

9. Light is not a “speed limit” but an “observation limit”; it doesn’t prove a physical connection between space and time. Time is the observation of changes in space, and therefore there is a dilation effect upon the space due to the dilation on the observation of motion in time. The time is dilating due to the “physical” (aka mathematical³⁶) effect upon the internal field structure of the light as its circuit is drained by successive loads:
 - a. Charged cosmic “dust” (ions)
 - b. Baryons
 - c. Electromagnetic fields
 - d. Charged plasma in dark or glow mode
 - e. Neutrinos and other charges
10. Intrinsic Redshift combined with Doppler Redshift will show that while the Universe is vast, it is not as vast as supposed (on the one hand). However, using light to define an origin of the Universe is a fallacy, even though the “Methuselah Star” is not as old/far as supposed. Big Bang is a logical fallacy, and mathematically inconsistent with “black Hole Theory”, itself a poor replacement for “white hole theory” which is a very poor replacement of plasmoid+marklund theory and the Lerner/Alfven understanding of plasma quasar/stellar object issue.

Photonic Model of Quanta

The work on discrete quanta goes back to the 1880s, which is, sad to say, still before the proven atomic models. What was advanced even by Weber was not experimentally accepted. Therefore, when the quanta was discovered, nobody really understood what to do with it. After the electron was “discovered” and later shown to be the source for electric “motion”, and proved *in situ* with electronics and power generation, and later signals as a field of study, it was surmised that the electron was quanta. However, Planck showed the distances of quantum “motion” was smaller even than the measured “size” of the electron! The size of the electron is, itself, quite a controversial subject and is our current real limit of observation. It is *probably* merely the electroweak field around the electron which is forming its size, and it actually is “physically” the size of the Planck length. This would tie electricity to light more obviously, and after all, explain why electric circuits propagate field waves at $1/c * \text{distance}$, and before the “physical” electrons “move” in the circuit. At present SM still models the electrons as tiny balls flowing, though we now know certainly that they “travel” on the surface of the conductors, not

³⁶ “Mathematics does not rule process. They happen regardless of mathematics. Further mathematics simplifies the description of transform between one state and the next. Transform in this context are the electric and magnetic field oscillations that occur and the translocation of the field(s) generator from one physical place to another physical place. While there is a “load” that affects the photon the photon is also a load on the media though which it travels. The period of interaction is very, very short hence the transfer of energy is slow. That started energy is absorbed by the photon from the media though which it travels and energy is expressed into the media though which it travels the question is which flow is dominate and what is the quantity factor difference between absorption and expression and this must conform to thermodynamic requirements. Frequency will tend to decrease unless the media has a high and unstable energy state under which condition the photon can be forced to absorb energy and thus increase in frequency. Exchange of energy between the media and photons is always bi-directional.”
~Ashcroft

through the interior. We *do* think that they move, as we have many working electronics from the TV to the scanning electron microscope reliant upon this model.

Nevertheless, the fact remains that as the atomic model progressed, it became clear that electrons lived in valence shells, and these shells changed to “arbitrary” (later identified as Platonic geometries[®], primarily), depending almost exclusively upon the gain or loss of quanta. These were named as a new ‘particle’ called photons.³⁷ If something is photonic then it indicates a quantum sized motion of discrete energy. We say discrete because it is not a smooth, analog curve, but a sudden shift in valence orbit, and the rules are fairly strict, but yet dynamic with thousands of variations (arbitrarily explained) per element, per molecule. The fact that elements were atoms was a big revelation. But the fact that isotopes were also elements was a little too inconvenient. Therefore the multi-neutron theory was “confirmed.” But why nuclei needed neutrons at all was not clear for some time, until the proton’s confirmation as the positive charge.

³⁷ “What is expressed here does not sit well with general understandings and I am not sure how to state it so that various positions expose themselves as invalid. This transition is not something that I am aware of. It does not sit correctly in the developments in understanding of electromagnetic radiation which is where the photons originates.

The quanta of energy concepts come from the interaction of light and matter in spectral along with chemical and nuclear analysis that occurred from 1848 through to 1937 when a more complete set of structures were realised. At that time fundamental particles were considered to be the Electron, Proton, Neutron, Photon and Neutrino. However all these particles were in fact constructs and thus not fundamental. What the components that produce the constructs actually are is a matter of conjectural debate. due to the fact that they are described as constructs, standing waves etc is not finalised and there is no settled science solution. Due to these underlying problems quantum speculations then move on to claim that these constructs are also also some form of standing wave or flow. Tesla made the claim to journalists that there was no such thing as a particle, it was a oscillating field flow. What we need to understand that there must be some sort of construction. This construction must be self confining. This self confined construction must permit fluid like behaviour that expressed standing wave behaviour. blar, blar, blar. We simply lack the data and understanding required to come to a conclusion that describes the construct required and the behavioural description that requires the observed behaviour to be present. A long way we are yet to travel.” ~Ashcroft

make instant changes to an orbit which is already “fuzzy” due to a fact of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle.

This is not an accident

It is the same principle for why we know the SAM is a better model for the nucleus: it relieves us of arbitrariness, and admits not only the elemental nature of isotopes but all the other topes.

>>It also permits us to understand the philosophical and metaphysical nature of the plasma by correctly identifying ions as elements - atomic, isotopic, or molecular - seeking electron *pacification*, owing in no small part to their desire for electric connection, under *magnetic influence*, in circuit modeling<<

This is absolutely key.

It’s the Thermodynamics, Dummy

Reproducing this from my previous paper on the pseudoscience of “Dark photons”:

Table 1 :: Rates of c in various materials

Material	v _L (km/s)	% less than c (in vacuum, 299,792.5)
Plasma/Solar Wind	299,000	0.26%
Air (ground level)	299,700	0.03%
Water	225,000	24.9%
Glass (clear)	200,000	33.3%
Fiber ⁴¹	204,190	31.8%
Crystal (diamond)	124,000	58.6%
Copper (electrons)	299,792	0.01-0.03% ⁴²

The remaining implication, therefore, is that astrophysicists are “barking up the wrong tree” with trying to turn photons into massive particles (rather than ‘particles’ with eV values) which can then act as the “missing matter” from the galaxy haloes. It isn’t even a relevant discussion to begin with!

⁴¹ <https://www.quora.com/What-is-precisely-the-speed-of-light-in-fiber-optics>

⁴² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Speed_of_electricity

The point is that if the “particle” has to instantly decelerate, this is impossible, but if it then has to instantly re-accelerate, this has no basis in reality. Forget the maintenance of atoms, the Vacuum Energy would be depleted merely from the continual usage to maintain light’s prolific speed.

We really do not need to go any deeper than this, but let us remind the reader of the “slow motion” experiments showing, conclusively, that light does not emerge in slow motion out of the Coke bottle to then bounce off the surface ahead, like a tennis ball would, but actually *instantly* reflects upon the table surface, despite refraction through a medium and so called “slow motion”! This is visual proof of the issue.⁴³

Figure 1 - Speed of Lights vs Intensity; proof that photonic particles would break the law of conservation of energy-mass; Credit: Author

⁴³ “There are multiple processes in play, and this has been known since Newton. ElectroMagnetic Radiation (cf light) interacts with media in a variety of ways. Reflection, Refraction, Diffraction, Absorption All these process occur during the interaction, and all of these processes produce a dual direction exchange of energy that obeys the understanding of thermodynamics. There is no instant change at any time. A proper description of required behaviour would deliver this consequence. The fact that equipment does not clock fast enough to provide data in conformance of Nyquist Theorems of data acquisition does not mean the consequential behaviour is not present.” ~Ashcroft

Figure 2 - Slow motion light, clearly reaching the desk “ahead” of the pulse, no photo pulse seen emerging or slowed by the coke bottle (no lag) ([gif](#)); credit: MIT⁴⁴

No mass, No momentum

Mass is clearly not a weight, per se, as weight is a measure of attraction, gravitically, between an object on Earth. It is, instead, a measure of charge level of an object. If a star is more charged, i.e. a white dwarf, blue hypergiant, or pulsar, or magnetar, or “neutron star”, then it will have more mass than less charged stars. Its reconfiguration and behavior is the subject of a different PEMF discussion, so I will refer the reader to the work of Donald Scott’s “The Electric Sky” and my paper on “Magnetic Universe Theory.”

What is pertinent is that mass comes from charge. Fields come from charge. Forces come from energy motions, and that comes from charge. Therefore, if a photon has 0 mass, it must be instead something other than matter, and cannot therefore be a particle or wave. It is simply something one can sometimes model as a particle, sometimes as a wave. It is this simple. Photons are not imparting momentum, they are circuits carrying charge, and depositing them on loads. Therefore, the Voyager spacecrafts drift because the solar charges (light and particles/ions) are deposited upon the craft. Over time this charge separates so that one side of the craft is slightly more positive, and one side slightly more negative. In the presence of the solar electric field, there is a net force, and the Biefeld-Brown effect is observed to create drift. It doesn’t make Newton wrong and Hawking right. It makes the SM wrong.

$$P=MV, \text{ where } V=d/t \text{ and } M=0. \text{ Therefore } P = 0. \quad (3)$$

⁴⁴ <https://www.livescience.com/65113-fastest-camera-captures-speed-of-light.html>

Macrolensing is a Farce, It is Refraction in a Plasma-electromagnetic Medium

The fact that this discussion has to be had, in 2022, is a sign of how bad astrophysics has become in terms of basic physics.

Let's look at this from the equations of Newton, Poincare, Einstein, Planck, Gauss, and Hertz:

Table 2 :: Comparisons of Mathematical Models

Newton (4) Gravity	Poincare (5) energy-mass	Einstein (6) dilation	Planck (7) Wave theory	Gauss (8) Electric field	Hertz (9) Electric force
$F = \frac{GMm}{r^2}$	$M = \frac{e}{c^2}$	$t' = \frac{t}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$	$e = h\nu$	$Ef = \frac{kQR}{r^2}$	$F = \frac{Qq}{4\pi\epsilon r^2}$

In all of these theories, G only appears in the first, and bear in mind Newton did not know what mass was or how it performed what is now known as “spooky action at a distance.”

He never said he had **the** answer. He only maintained that this equation would, in effect, explain the *why* of Kepler's Laws of Motion. But, in fact, they only delayed the answering. G was a stand in. Nowhere in special relativity, or mass-energy relation, or anything else involving degradation by r^2 , do you need gravity. Einstein's choosing of this for “General Relativity” was not only controversial, it was doomed to failure, or again, behaving as a stop gap to explain what is clearly PEM behavior in light. While we do not understand 100% why light behaves as a wave in EMF/EMR the fact remains is it is electromagnetic, and as one can plainly see: there is no G in those equations.

“But the space time *bends*” is the argument. Well, setting aside the arbitrariness of bent “up-down” sheets in arbitrary space, or the impossibility of 1st order differential invariants in unimodular coordinates, the fact is that if this were so, then all things would accelerate inward towards the massive object, in perpetuity. Yet, the moon, for example, is evacuating its orbit of the Earth, and is not even in a stable orbit⁴⁵. Rather, a conservation of angular and energy-momentum should be sought, as was by Hannes Alven, in conjunction with a PEMF solution set to why “gravitation” is occurring⁴⁶. Not the other way around. As the late great E. Dowdye⁴⁷ showed in his “Extinction Principle” you do not need relativity for lensing, you only need refraction. It refracts because of the laws of optics, and the PEM fields surrounding stars. The more charge, the more pinch, the more field presence, the more bending of light.

A Thought Experiment

Einstein was fond of his thought-clocks hanging in space. What a useless exercise. However, let us propose a thought experiment which actually can be done at least in spirit. We

⁴⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Orbit_of_the_Moon

⁴⁶ “On the Cosmogony of the Solar System,” H. Alfvén, 1945-1946

⁴⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/dowdye>

have a defined source, let us say that it's a circular source, with a defined area A. Due to the nature of the material, it has a dense packing, such that the source diodes happen to be the size of the Planck length.

We have a detector which is variable and has an expanding surface area B whose area increases exponentially vs. A, moving at a defined rate from $d=0$ to $d=$ practically infinite.

At $d=0$, $A=B$, and 100% of the photons will reach the detector, and the chamber is a perfect vacuum.

Figure 3 - Surface area of Detector vs Source A, as D increases

As the detector moves away from the source, the light spreads out in the chamber. So it is not a laser.

At what distance does the trigonometry of the situation dictate that the spread of the light will create gaps between the photons, such that a mottling or concentration due to wave diffraction, will become apparent?

The answer is "at no distance." The detector will remain completely lit with even lighting at all distances, with its reflective surface decreasing in luminosity as the light is diffused to cover the entire surface at a distance.

Now, if we do the same experiment with a spherical source, and a spherical room as detector, as the sun and space around it, we have an even more distinct demonstration of the issue. The issue is that the reflective surface has an *electrical relationship* with the source, and with us, the observers, affected of course by dilation due to the rate of induction in the medium. This relationship pre-defines the behavior of light not as a concentrating series of balls, but as a generally diffuse reflective circuit. Each atom is a load with a resistance R (in ohms). The rotation of the light is proven, with polar sunglasses/filter no less, to be solely a matter of the 90° rotation in the Lorentzian behavior of the light. This, as discussed, was shown by Distinti to be a matter of an inverted, rotated identity matrix⁴⁸, predefining the imaginary number as a real behavior of the Force⁴⁹, whether the electric and magnetic fields are in parallel (and counter rotating), or perpendicular. The perpendicular may only be a model of the Bessel function behavior of the light (coaxial)⁵⁰, or it may be real. But it is rotated and inverted.

We know this occurs or else we could not generate electricity, and this document could not be written, much less sustained.

⁴⁸ "Vortex Algebra," R. Distinti, 2019

⁴⁹ Euler's formula: <https://www.britannica.com/science/Eulers-formula>

⁵⁰ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/thunderbolts-project/donald-scott>

Therefore, the reflective surface reflects not balls, but circuit behavior, and that behavior is related to the rate of induction in the medium, *c*. **It has nothing whatsoever to do with G**. It never did.

Intrinsic Redshift

This is not a treatise on IR, nor IRDR. Such a treatment has already been provided, rotely, by the late great ‘Galileo of the 20th Century’ and by H. Arp in his seminal work, “Seeing Red.”⁵¹ Nevertheless, we need to do one or two things. First, distinguish this from the concept of “tired light” which was discluded.⁵² For starters, it is not that the light is tired, it is drained. You need to sleep everyday, no matter how tired you are. However, being a drained source is a matter of physics whether in the body or any other circuit. The fact is that energy dissipates. Now, this isn’t the paper to discuss Cosmic Rearrangement and Two Way Entropy⁵³, that will accompany this one. But we should mention that it is a Law of Thermodynamics⁵⁴ that in this *matter based* domain we presently call our Universe, excluding the counterspace but including the Aether, which has been verified by a 2nd (and 3rd⁵⁵) vertical interferometer experiment⁵⁶ entropy always increases. Always.

Therefore, it isn’t really a surprise that light *frequency* shifts either via distance or due to intrinsic properties of the light owing to its charge and proximal relationship to a source. A source, in Arp’s case, being the galactic or quasar center. For our purposes, simply light sources

such as incandescents or fluorescents or diodes, etc. The light is going to intrinsically shift, because it encounters hysteresis⁵⁷ within the circuit, as has been known since Steinmetz.⁵⁸ Therefore, astrophysicists should adjust their models based on Arp’s work, and after dealing with the non-existence of the CMBR⁵⁹, (either use a Herouni angled scope⁶⁰ or do it from outside the Earth’s atmosphere⁶²) then redraw the “shape of the Universe”.

Figure 4 - Herouni Scope which dismayed CMBR; credit: RT.com⁶³

⁵¹ <https://www.amazon.com/Seeing-Red-Redshifts-Cosmology-Academic/dp/0968368905>

⁵² <https://www.science.org/content/article/tired-light-hypothesis-gets-re-tired>

⁵³ <https://bit.ly/3llcHzy>

⁵⁴ “Magnetic Universe Theory,” Appendix B.II, pp. 135

⁵⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7T0d7o8X2-E>

⁵⁶ <https://disk.yandex.ru/i/FnUkHxw15C5EIg>

⁵⁷ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0304885308004150>

⁵⁸ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/steinmetz>

⁵⁹ <https://vixra.org/abs/1310.0120>

⁶⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p8IKQMEYYLw>

⁶¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lpTQsWD0LDQ>

⁶² Like James Webb Telescope, but designed to look for CMBR

⁶³ <https://www.rt.com/news/463513-radio-telescope-soviet-armenia/>

Also, we need to understand, when it comes to this behavior inside the distances of the atom or less, it is so negligible that we will not need any relativistic effects inside the microscopic, because there is, in effect, nothing to drain the sources (each other), and they are constantly receiving energy from the Aether. The exchange of Aether > reality > entropy > counterspace > Aether is most likely nearly balanced. It may be that antimatter is the trailing ledger in that account, we do not know because we do not have a good model for SCS or an anatomy for the Aether. Therefore, there is not much else to do but note the ratio of matter to antimatter and try to find a balancing trend, to calculate the in between of Marklund events⁶⁴ on the SGEC⁶⁵ and Universal scale. How often It All pulse-modulates is of course, not clear. And doppler redshift is inadequate to give a date be it billions or trillions of years. However, all the waves are co-modulated, meaning that they are both sinusoidal and yet amplitudinal and frequency shifted, depending on scale, zoom, and magneto-materio reconfiguration. The magnetics lags the electric by 90 degrees phase, but then rearranges the material mediums and energy matrices, which determines new forming, latent, or dying connections.

Figure 5 - Marklund Convection;
credit: Chris Reeve

This is also an intrinsic property, and is related to the fundamental nature of the Changes. It doesn't just present us with time, but with observational limits and "graininess." Conflating this finite approximation with the CMBR is a colossal mistake; and then leapfrogging from there to a Holographic/Simulated Universe is another. But the behavior of holograms - and for that matter the magic of superconductivity - do indicate, again, that the nature of charge and light are little understood, even if we can use them.

No, Light is not a Wave, either

One thing that should be made clear is that a wave is not *isness*. Meaning light is not a wave, but can be modeled as a wave. A wave carries energy or information, and is an expression of the Laws of Rotation, and of Vibration (frequency). Nothing moves in a straight line, but we see the attempts of nature to conform to them. But that is a delusion because

⁶⁴ <https://youtu.be/sIQRBrmEIXo>

⁶⁵ Superagalactic Electric Circuit

electron scanning microscopy shows us the jagged edges of all things, and reveals their fractal natures.

Why fractal? The fractal behaviors of the material is only approximating the mathematical truths, particularly the golden ratio.

$$\phi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2} \quad (10)$$

Their actual revelation is less than perfect, but the underlying data is Truth itself. Hence the Power of Numbers modulates the Power of the Force and it does so through the Aether. The Aether, therefore, will almost certainly be our “quantum foam” that is to say, quantized distances of vibrations of the Aether in response to the re-emergence of energy (pure to us, 100% Entropy to the counterspace) through the PEMbrane. This is not to be confused with the branes of SUSY/String Theory, although the idea is not all wrong:

Table 3 :: Comparisons of PEMC and SM

<i>PEM Cosmology</i>	<i>Standard Model</i>
Super Marklund-Lerner event	Big Bang
Bostickian Super Plasmoids	Black Holes
Magnetars, etc.: all highly charged	Neutron Stars
PEMbrane re-emersion from SCS	Quantum foam
Counterspace	Vacuum Energy
Aether	Space-time
Baryonic matter, plasma dust, ions	Dark Matter
Magnetism / SGEC fields and circuits	Dark Energy
Rate of induction in medium X	Speed of Light
Electron-Positron Pair	Neutron
1 form of Ultracold plasma	Bose-einstein Condensate
Liquid Crystal Hot Plasma	Liquid Metallic Hydrogen
PEMBrane	Brane

As you can see from the color coding, the SM is full of internal contradictions. Whereas the left column is all 100% centered around a Unified Aether Field Theory known as **Plasma-electromagnetism**. Its behaviors are fractal and self-similar at all scales, though their outer forms are repetitiously-chaotic and variable in observational expectation. Within a similar scale, experiments repeat outcomes. On different scales one *may* get differing results. In all zooms, one will have observational alterations because of: curl, divergence, dilation,

capacitance, inductance, transformation, and the relationship of: conduction, impedance, diamagnetism, and dielectricity due to the counterspatial behaviors of the circuit. In our case, light. But not all circuits are similar in their form. All circuits *are similar* in their circuitousness, preservation of energy-momentum, conservation of ME, and of course circuit behaviors ($V=IR$ and RLC et al., in effect).

Table 4 :: These Things Do Not Exist

Cold Dark Matter [@]	Dark Energy	New Dark Energy
Dark Photons	Negative Mass	Charged Dark Matter
Zero Particles	Tachyons	Strings
Virtual Particles	Classical Black Holes	Wormholes
Axions	WIMPs	MACHOS

@ as said before... why not use GNOMES if you just need a pulling force to suddenly push? :)

So, what is Light?

This leads us to our final discussion. What the heck is Light?

>>It is a circuit<<

The Field is a relationship.

The relationship is Source and Load.

The Force is resolving imbalance while creating new imbalance

A Circuit as a Physical Model of Light

The issue is that we have treated electricity as *that thing which runs modern life only on a human level*. This is, of course, now out-dated nonsense both scientifically, and culturally. We are economically dependent on the Force, and we are spiritually cognizant of it, albeit couched in multivarious linguistic and symbolic terms.

Nevertheless, a circuit is something measurable, defined, and scientific in its mode. Engineers use them in order to make the world work better for humans. Therefore, mimsically speaking, there is a distinct proportionate response by the Universe, or Source, and those that acknowledge the Truth and use it correctly.⁶⁶

Figure 6 - example Feynman Diagram; credit: wiki⁶⁷

⁶⁶ Those that do not, the Nei Yeh maintains, perish.

⁶⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Feynman_diagram

Therefore, let us consider Feynman's perspective, and consider Birkeland's "current" perspective.

Feynman envisioned light as an expulsion of remnant charges, termed now as quarks (Gellman, et al.) and other particles, as a remainder of the "event" of the interaction of these "smashings", forced using - you guessed it - the PEMF and intense magnetic fields. These expelled remnants could be measured, however brief, and then used to make predictions about future quantum sized events. These diagrams became the standard for QED and later QCD modeling of atoms. I expect they will continue to be useful circuit "snapshots" (part of the entire process), well into the merger of all QED and QCD with PEMC over the next 100 years. But I caution: Feynman confined himself to 3 dimensions of magnetism, but only 1 dimension of electricity. This will prove insufficient at Stage 2 of SPACER civilization⁶⁸ and perhaps before that. Already we are encountering issues in PCB production relating to quantum light bending effects (gravity indeed!), and the limits will need serious fractal/recursive modeling by quantum computers to resolve beyond a certain limit. As of yet, though, our computing progress continues, unmolested. In fact we are beating Moore's Law.⁶⁹

Birkeland, by contrast (and therefore D. Scott and others) envision a coaxial, counter-rotational or "vortex" behavior in the light, which enables the same polarization, but doesn't require a particle to make irrational turns without losing energy... and the model also requires no mass, because it is **primarily defined by charge**.

Figure 7 - SM vision of EM Wave ([gif](#)); credit: Wiki

It also, inherently, allows for intrinsic degradation of the light as the electrical power drops off at a much more sustainable function of $R^{-1/2}$, instead of R^2 . This is key, because it

⁶⁸ https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System

⁶⁹ <https://matmatch.com/resources/blog/what-will-we-do-when-moores-law-is-no-more/>

enables electricity to travel vast cosmic distances. It also means no matter how far light travels, it will logarithmically decay.⁷⁰

Kirchoff's Failure

The main person who missed this opportunity is none other than the creator of Circuit Laws, Kirchoff. While he was controversial in discovering them⁷¹, and promulgating them, he got away scott free with some optical impossibilities which violate the 5 laws of thermodynamics⁷²... and he didn't even do the experiments to validate his own Thermal Law! In fact, spectroscopists, and even Planck just *accepted* his ideas because of his personage and fame, and no one invalidated them until Dr. Pierre-Marie Robitaille showed conclusively that the "Law" was nothing of the sort.

Table 5 :: Robitaille's Kirchoff Experiments

Figures 8 - 10: Robitaille vs. Kirchoff; and Planck; credit: P.M. Robitaille

How a man who came so close to immortal fame as the guy who discovered the true nature of light, made such a colossal blunder, would be a neat journey of research into his writings, and I encourage our audience to do so and report back to me. Suffice it to say, the following is **not** true:

"For a body of any arbitrary material emitting and absorbing thermal electromagnetic radiation at every wavelength in thermodynamic equilibrium, the ratio of its emissive

⁷⁰ "This does not happen for a photon, This behaviour is due to the spread of all photons through a spheroid surface that surrounds a source. It is intensity of light that changes and the factor of diminution is none of those listed. Photons a singleton constructions that travel in a helix conduit from on location to another. They can gain or loose energy if they interact with other constructs along the helix conduit. What decays is the quantity of energy captured in the frequency in oscillation and this does not diminish to zero, ever.

The only problem I have is is the travel of a photon an electromagnetic discharge between two location of different potential. This may well be what is happening and it will require a very different understanding of what electromagnetic capacitance structures exist in the universe and it is clear that the layout of the capacitors changes dramatically due to scale." ~Ashcroft

⁷¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TFP55200MPY>

⁷² https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gvr_BcH1Cmw&list=PLnU8XK0C8oTAxK4bT4S7WT_SCgG3ZS-Uy

*power to its dimensionless coefficient of absorption is equal to a universal function only of radiative wavelength and temperature. That universal function describes the perfect black-body emissive power.*⁷³

This does not hold experimentally, when using IR detectors to observe black bodies. Note he wrote this in 1860, 17 years before quantized light, 30 years before electrons being proved, and 50 years before modern atoms. How scandalous that he got away with it scott free. How sad for mankind that we have based Big Bang on these three defunct legs, and all have fallen flat:

- Doppler redshift of light
- Cosmic Background Radiation = Big Bang
- Michelson-Morley, a *horizontal* interferometer experiment which ignores the uniform density of Aether expected at the same elevation.

>>We have wasted 100+ years in development.<<

- ❖ Real Black Bodies can do work
- ❖ Perfect Reflectors cannot (no load/impedance)

A Circuit as a Metaphysical Model of Light

We leave now, for the moment, the PEMC realm of science, and enter the EPEMC/MIMS⁷⁴ world of metaphysics. Why? Because it is what Gilbert, Newton, and Tesla would do.

There is a concept I would like to give a different perspective on light. That is a yang aspect, meaning unified and undifferentiated. Meaning alchemical. In this perspective, the light is merely a peeling back of the barrier or obscuration provided by our mundane reality. This works with the circuit model by revealing the aspect of the Logos being the Light giving Lord. Let us term this, conveniently, as LLL theory. Is it an wonder, for you alchemists out there:

- ❖ Inductance is symbolized by the letter L

Let us look at the formula for inductance: $L = \frac{\Phi(I)}{I}$, where I is the current. (11)

Now, the numerator means the “magnetic flux of the current”. In other words the electrical current is induced by the magnetic flux.

But, demonstrably magnetism itself is not flowing⁷⁵; it is responding to the changing surface currents. Magnetic flux is a model. The field, if left to its own, is static. So what do we mean? We mean to say that the magnetism is flowing as a circuit itself, with a relationship between the polar aspects of the Force. We use north and south by convention, but might as well use yin and yang. Nevertheless, the relationship is in continual circuitous form, and this creates an electrical connection. A charge may stand alone, but it is always in relationship to the

⁷³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kirchhoff%27s_law_of_thermal_radiation

⁷⁴ Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual (an EPEMC philosophy)

⁷⁵ But instead a phase state change in crystal behavior and surface circuits.

other charges. But a pole may never stand alone. Isn't this **Love**? Maybe we should call it L⁴ theory...

Whatever the case may be, the inducted electrical relationship requires both poles to be in flux, and flux is Change in the passage of time and is covered in the Wind trigram or "Law of Evolutionary Flux." Is it any wonder that the wind carries charges, change, and disease? All are associations with wind, which follows pressure gradients. Again, seeking, but never creating equalization or real homeostasis. Isn't it true that being "in Love" means appreciating each other's differences and steadily becoming like equals, but also having a little more to explore?

Spirituality, Revelation, And Living Within the Light, etc.

Living "in the light" has long had a meaning in spirituality. Lightness itself goes back to Genesis and before that text, the discussion of the light feather one would be weighed against in the Judgment by Anubis⁷⁶. What then, is this lightness? It is the feeling of freedom from a heart discharged of regret, worry, and sin accumulated in life. One can accumulate by injecting light of bad self or other observations through the eyes (optical sensors), or ears (vibrational sensors which convert sound to electricity). One can discharge via prayer, repentance, meditation, etc. Whatever the Way, the heart is lifted, and the purkinje fibers are strengthened, or protected a while longer. The heart becomes capable of carrying greater and greater loads with more practice with Tao, called now Te⁷⁷. The symbol for Te is phallic, but originally was the streaming of plasma material between Mars and Venus⁷⁸, meaning combat strength. Bellicosity is the result of excess charge in the chest (middle dan tian)⁷⁹. This is the place, however, that the transformation of self occurs, and where the Temple is said to resolve. If the Qi is in the chest, one becomes a Sage, and the world is said to revolve around one, and not disturb one. The body, but especially the heart, is proliferated by Charge Distributive Networks⁸⁰, and the heart-mind is connected to the Central Nervous System, all called the Fire phase (or plasma phase⁸¹) by the Chinese medical doctors.

Revealing the light means living with Truth, and the next meaning of Te is two eyes with the ability to look a man in the eyes and see lies or truth. This gives one the ability known as Tong Shen Ming⁸² or Penetrating Spirit Brightness/Light, and Ming is also a double meaning of Destiny. Destiny is revealed to one through the "lifting of the veil on the eyes" in the reality moment (dzogchen⁸³ or zen), which clears the sinner of wrongdoing by ceasing to lie to God.

The circuit of these statements come round back and forth, over and over again, because the PEM (Force) is next after Lord, and level with Physics by way of GOD (G power), the /|\ itself. Note that the Broaddus awen is placed at the head level of Christ in the Northern

⁷⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Weighing_of_souls

⁷⁷ 德 - meaning inner power or strength

⁷⁸ https://www.academia.edu/38268897/Sumo_Ancient_Ritual_to_the_Thunder_God

⁷⁹ <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

⁸⁰

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_%27structure%27_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

⁸¹ https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram

⁸² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7L2WN8m4juQ>

⁸³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dzogchen>

Cross by the Madoc Ft. Ancient, for a reason.⁸⁴ The /|\ is the “triple godhead” which is, in India, the conversion of Indra into: Brahma, Vishnu, Shiva. The Indra is the Shamash star⁸⁵, and the other three are its first birthed gas giants, Saturn, Jupiter, and Neptune.⁸⁶

Thus living within the light means directly, and not tangentially, understanding the PEMF that controls the cosmos. Ergo why the Chinese said the Shang Di was Heaven⁸⁷ which held the gas “stars”, and why Moses forbade the Jews from worshiping Venus and of course doing human sacrifice as much of the world did, when they ripped out hearts. These things Are. You do not need to accept them. But it might help you, if you did.

Colloquial Expressionism

We say things like “I feel lighter already” and “lighten your load” and do not stop to marvel at the simple simplicity of understanding revealed. This is because charlatans and sophists have stolen science to make Scientism⁸⁸, and now we see the negative effects of irrational (socialist) education via propaganda. It is destroying society

Therefore, whenever you see a colloquialism about light, lightness, lightning, enlightenment, etc. think to yourself about the potentiality of living L⁴ revelation that might be occurring. Bear in mind that there is no way to describe electricity without waves, and no way to describe waves without Euler’s formula, and no way to do that with the “imaginary” number. So what seems silly might be more real than you can possibly imagine.

Psychological Impressionism

Letting “the Light” penetrate your eyes seems obvious. You can stare into the sun, or a light, or read a book until it glows. Or you can simply practice “turning the light around” and charge your heart up.⁸⁹ However, what I’d recommend first is familiarizing yourself with the “enemy” of the Light: Oblivion. Oblivion will keep the reader from understanding this text, or any text, and keep one in delusion and illusion. It will drive one to darkness, and to the dark side of the Force. If $F=ma$, then one will, by necessity, “accelerate” in the dark side. “Life in the Fast Lane” is known as a night life which destroys health and “burning the candle at both ends” also. meaning, in other words, that when one is drained of life giving light, and driven into the dark void, either as the self - to recharge in counterspace - or by the “Dark One” (Satan), which robs one of life’s joys. Be careful to “impress” and “imprint” light and lightness onto the self with not only humor and spirituality, but levity of character: charity, forgiveness, solace, friendship, etc.

Conclusions

The discussion of Light has been, based on these final paragraphs, definitely obscured by misunderstanding within physics and perhaps religion, too. To understand the “Big G” is to understand this important topic within the realm of science, and beyond it. It is to understand the

⁸⁴ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327424078_Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_-_Final

⁸⁵ https://www.academia.edu/70768047/Shamash_Proto_Saturn_OpEd

⁸⁶ https://www.academia.edu/50912947/The_Dwarf_Star_God_Origins_slideshow

⁸⁷ https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao

⁸⁸ <https://pediiaa.com/what-is-the-difference-between-science-and-scientism/>

⁸⁹ <https://www.amazon.com/Secret-Golden-Flower-Thomas-Cleary/dp/0062501933/>

relationships of the Polar laws and principles (of the P power), with the other powers, and the forces, especially (F Power). Note that it is through God (G power), which is the grandiose extension of consciousness, typified by the Lord (L power; $L^5?$). This means understanding consciousness under that power as a circuit, as well as light as a circuit. These are not accidental coincidences but wholly related to plasmascript runes, and observational mytho-historical facts seen worldwide. But, for us, we are most interested in the light-circuit model, and the rate of induction in the medium. The main medium is, of course, the Aether (A power), but not only it. However, it cannot be a particle, or this would violate the P power's laws of thermodynamics. Therefore, we seek a massless definition, which, of course, enables us to understand mass without using it to define itself, and this betters our understanding of matter as well by enabling us to use SAM in a PEMC compliant⁹⁰ model to relate mass to **charge**. And not to weight or gravity, itself a placeholder idea for figuring out Kepler's Motion⁹¹ in an era previous to acceptance of the clearly superior atomic model (to the Aristotelian model). Finally, I conjecture that living in the revealing circuit nature of light will help the individual, and society, to conform to the Laws/Principles. That is, as it happens what the data (part of N power) says, too, both mytho-historically, mimsically, and in operations management.

References

1. "Scientists discover how to turn light into matter after 80-year quest," Imperial College UK News, G. Wilson, 2014, <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/news/149087/scientists-discover-turn-light-into-matter/>
2. "Response to Crother's Exposition of Unimodular Defect," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/68876325/Response_to_Crothers_Exposition_of_Unimodular_Defect
3. "Physics and metaphysics of Aristotle," Britannica.com., <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Aristotle/Physics-and-metaphysics>
4. "Opticks," Dover Publications, Sir Isaac Newton, 1952, <http://strangebeautiful.com/other-texts/newton-opticks-4ed.pdf>
5. "Wilhelm Weber's Main Works on Electrodynamics," Volume I: Gauss and Weber's Absolute System of Units, Published by C. Roy Keys Inc., 2021, <https://www.ifi.unicamp.br/~assis/Weber-in-English-Vol-1.pdf>
6. "The Explanatory Power of the Structured Atom Model (SAM)," J.E. Kaal et al., <http://ikkem.com/iccf23/orppt/ICCF23-OA-04%20Kaal.pdf>
7. "The Structured Atom Model," Structured Atom.org., <https://structuredatom.org/>
8. "Structured Atom Model Overview," Ethereal Matters, <https://etherealmatters.org/sam>
9. "Carbon 12," Structured Atom.org., <https://structuredatom.org/atomizer/atom-viewer>
10. "Structured Atomic Model," (EPEMC) Gateway) Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/atomic-models/sam>
11. "Velikovsky," (EPEMC) Gateway, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/velikovsky>
12. "MHD - Proof of electric currents in space," H. Alfven, (EPEMC) Gateway, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pu-research/h-alfven>

⁹⁰ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards>

⁹¹ <https://www.math.ksu.edu/~dbski/writings/planetary.pdf>

13. "On the magnet, magnetick bodies also, and on the great magnet the earth a new physiology, demonstrated by many arguments & experiments," Chiswick Press, W. Gilbert, 2010, <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1A9oPx8jSE3hAYyiykSbGY7L13KiSncii/view>
14. "Magnetic Universe Theory A Top-Down Review of Phases of Magnetic Theory Development, with accompanying historiography and comparison with Unified/Aether Field Theories including EPEMC," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC
15. Newton: 17th century, EM theory: 19th Century
16. "MIMS 2+ : Applications and Discussions," Academia, Sf R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions
17. "How Scientists Discovered Helium, the First Alien Element, 150 Years Ago," Smithsonian Magazine, L. Boissoneault, 2018, <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/how-scientists-discovered-helium-first-alien-element-1868-180970057/>
18. "The Forgotten Genius of Oliver Heaviside: A Maverick of Electrical Science," European Mathematical Society, A. Bultheel, 2018, <https://euro-math-soc.eu/review/forgotten-genius-oliver-heaviside-maverick-electrical-science>
19. "Fusors," (EPEMC) Gateway, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pu-research/fusors>
20. "Physicists led by University of Iowa more fully describe sun's electric field," Iowa Now, R. C. Lewis, 2021, <https://now.uiowa.edu/2021/07/physicists-led-university-iowa-more-fully-describe-suns-electric-field>
21. "Weber," (EPEMC) Gateway, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/weber>
22. "Pierre-Marie Robitaille," (EPEMC) Gateway, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/robitaille>
23. "Discovered by Boltzmann: History of quantum mechanics," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_quantum_mechanics
24. "Planck length," Britannica.com., <https://www.britannica.com/science/Planck-length>
25. "The Mass of the Photon," Institute of Physics Publishing: Phys. 68, L.-Cheng Tu, J.Luo, & G. T Gillies, 2004, <https://www.princeton.edu/~romalis/PHYS312/Coulomb%20Ref/Photonmasslimits.pdf>
26. "TT Brown: Biefeld-Brown Effect," (EPEMC) Gateway, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/tt-brown>
27. "Discourses & Mathematical Illustrations pertaining to Extinction Shift Principle 2nd Edition," Amazon, E. H. Dowdye, <https://www.amazon.com/Discourses-Mathematical-Illustrations-Electrodynamics-Transformations/dp/0963447157/>
28. "Four decades of Gluons," Cern, A. Lopes, 2019, <https://home.cern/news/news/physics/four-decades-gluons>
29. "Quark: Subatomic Particle," The Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica, 2021, <https://www.britannica.com/science/quark>
30. "What is precisely the speed of light in fiber optics?," Quora, K. Lundgren, 2020, <https://www.quora.com/What-is-precisely-the-speed-of-light-in-fiber-optics>
31. "Speed of electricity." Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Speed_of_electricity
32. "Here's What the Speed of Light Looks Like in Slow Motion," Live Science, B. Specktor, 2019, <https://www.livescience.com/65113-fastest-camera-captures-speed-of-light.html>
33. "Orbit of the Moon," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Orbit_of_the_Moon
34. On the Cosmogony of the Solar System," H. Alfven, 1945-1946
35. "Dr. Edward Dowdye," (EPEMC) Gateway, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/dowdye>
36. "Vortrix Algebra," R. Distinti, 2019

37. "Euler's formula". The Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica, 2021, <https://www.britannica.com/science/Eulers-formula>
38. "Donald Scott & Eric Lerner," (EPEMC) Gateway, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/thunderbolts-project/donald-scott>
39. "Seeing Red: Redshifts, Cosmology and Academic Science," Amazon, H. Arp, 1997, <https://www.amazon.com/Seeing-Red-Redshifts-Cosmology-Academic/dp/0968368905>
40. "Tired-Light" Hypothesis Gets Re-Tired: Theory disputing the expanding universe suffers a double punch," Science.org., C. Seife, 2001, <https://www.science.org/content/article/tired-light-hypothesis-gets-re-tired>
41. "EPEMC - Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://bit.ly/3llcHzy>
42. Magnetic Universe Theory," Appendix B.II, pp. 135
43. "Extended Michelson-Morley Interferometer experiment. English version," Youtube, 2009, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7T0d7o8X2-E>
44. "The Birth Of The Universe (sub).mp4," <https://disk.yandex.ru/i/FnUkHxw15C5EIg>
45. "On the Steinmetz hysteresis law," Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials Volume 320, Issue 20, F.J.G. Landgraf, M. Emura & M. F.de Campos, 2008, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0304885308004150>
46. "Steinmetz: A Giant Among Men," (EPEMC) Gateway, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/steinmetz>
47. "On the Origins of the CMB: Insight from the COBE, WMAP, and Relikt-1 Satellites," Progress in Physics, P.-Marie Robitaille, 2007, <https://vixra.org/abs/1310.0120>
48. "The Herouni Antenna - The Death of the Big Bang!" Youtube, 2019, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p8IKQMEYYLw>
49. "A Fading Relic of the Past: Retrospection - ROT-54/2.6," Youtube, H. Alaverdyan, 2016, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lptQsWD0LDQ>
50. "Drone VIDEO takes you up close to giant abandoned Soviet radio telescope in Armenia," RT.com., 2019, <https://www.rt.com/news/463513-radio-telescope-soviet-armenia/>
51. "Brief Summary & Visualization of the Marklund Convection - Birkeland Current Process," Youtube, C. Reeve, 2014, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sIQRBrmEIXo>
52. "Feynman diagram," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Feynman_diagram
53. "Conquering the Solar System," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System
54. "What Will We Do When Moore's Law Is No More?" Matmatch.com., B. Stafford, 2019, <https://matmatch.com/resources/blog/what-will-we-do-when-moores-law-is-no-more/>
55. "Spectroscopy Transformed Astronomy, Chemistry & Physics," Youtube, 2019, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TFP55200MPY>
56. "What is the 0th Law Of Thermodynamics? The Zeroth Law Explained!," Youtube, 2017, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gvr_Bch1Cmw&list=PLnU8XK0C8oTAXk4bT4S7WT_SCgG3_ZS-Uy
57. "Kirchhoff's law of thermal radiation," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kirchhoff%27s_law_of_thermal_radiation
58. "Weighing of souls," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Weighing_of_souls
59. "Sumo: Ancient Ritual to the Thunder God," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/38268897/Sumo_Ancient_Ritual_to_the_Thunder_God
60. "MIMS 2.2.1.1-3: The Threefold Science, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1LcH2FypSjl27RZYI8NnxqtXiHq8Ub7KsFrcRIRJ3pRE/edit>
61. "Charge Distribution Networks (CDN) as Meridians Utilizing conductivity as replacement 'structure' for meridians; comparison with neural, muscular, and fascial models," Research Gate, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_Conductivity_as_Replacement_Structure_for_Meridians_Comparison_with_Neural_Muscular_and_Fascial_Models
62. "MIMS 1.12 - Self-Consistency of the "Big G" Diagram," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram
63. "Tong Shen Ming," Youtube, D. Groves, 2010, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7L2WN8m4juQ>

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64. "Dzogchen," Wikipedia, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dzogchen>
65. "Great Pyramids of Kentucky - Final," Research Gate, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327424078_Great_Pyramids_of_Kentucky_-_Final
66. "Shamash Proto Saturn OpEd," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/70768047/Shamash_Proto_Saturn_OpEd
67. "The Dwarf Star God Origins (slideshow)," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, https://www.academia.edu/50912947/The_Dwarf_Star_God_Origins_slideshow
68. "Shang Di Heaven and Dao," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.academia.edu/38590072/Shang_Di_Heaven_and_Dao
69. "What is the Difference Between Science and Scientism," Pediaa.com., Hasa, 2019, <https://pediaa.com/what-is-the-difference-between-science-and-scientism/>
70. "The Secret of the Golden Flower," Amazon, T. Cleary, 1993, <https://www.amazon.com/Secret-Golden-Flower-Thomas-Cleary/dp/0062501933/>
71. "Standards: Easy Standards for researchers; EPEMC & MIMS," (EPEMC) Gateway, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards>
72. "Kepler's Laws of Planetary Motion and Newton's Law of Universal Gravitation," <https://www.math.ksu.edu/~dbski/writings/planetary.pdf>